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UPWARDS

Deliverable D2.4

Final report on WRF-LES and Park coupling

WP	2	Atmospheric model
Task	2.5	Interface between WRF-LES and turbine CFD model

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¹ Dissemination level: **PU** = Public. **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the JU). **RE** = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the JU). **CO** = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the JU)

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Deliverable abstract

This document is a **final report on WRF-LES and park coupling**, which we implemented in Task 2.5. Starting from the geo location of a planned wind park, the atmospheric model simulates spatial and temporal wind conditions (velocity, direction, pressure) on atmospheric scale. Based on these wind conditions, and based on a preconfigured set of wind turbines within the wind park, the park model simulates wind conditions on park and neighbourhood scale in between the wind turbines in terms of turbulent flow fields (velocity vectors, pressure). For this workflow step, the partner SINTEF provides solvers and models specialized on wind parks that can be executed by the Open Source simulation system OpenFoam.

Deliverable Review

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 2.4 documents the coupling of WRF-LES and park, which we implemented in Task 2.5. Starting from the geo location of a planned wind park, the atmospheric model simulates spatial and temporal wind conditions (velocity, direction, pressure) on atmospheric scale. The partner AWST provides a tailored version of the Open Source LES-simulation system WRF (Weather Research and Forecast Model - WRF-LES). Based on these wind conditions, and based on a preconfigured set of wind turbines within the wind park, the park model simulates wind conditions on park and neighbourhood scale in between the wind turbines in terms of turbulent flow fields (velocity vectors, pressure). For this workflow step, the partner SINTEF provides solvers and models specialized on wind parks that can be executed by the Open Source simulation system OpenFoam. The realization of this coupling contributes to the project Objective 3 of the Upwards agreement: “Generate in-depth knowledge of important wind turbine related physical phenomena through high fidelity simulations.”

2. Technical foundations of the coupling between atmospheric and park model

The explicit coupling between WRF-LES and Park model is a two-step workflow process:

1. Starting from the geographical location of a planned wind park, the **atmospheric model** simulates the realistic weather conditions occurring in the planetary boundary layer during a given episode of time in almost any region of the globe. The numerical domain span along an area of 6km x 6km that can cover the extension of a typical wind farm. Within that area, spatial and time-varying fields of velocity, direction, temperature, pressure (among others) are extracted, and post-processed to provide specific wind conditions which are later used as inputs to the **park model**.

As described in detail in D2.2, the atmospheric model is based on a Numerical Weather Prediction system called `WRF`⁴ (Weather Research and Forecasting). This model is open source, with centralized development by the U.S. National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) and the National Center for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) among other U.S. military and civilian Research Institutions, plus contributions provided by the scientific community.

The partner AWST provides a tailored version of the WRF system operating in Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) mode, together with a set of scripts to automatically prepare, operate and process the simulation outputs in order to produce the atmospheric conditions.

2. Based on these wind conditions, and based on a preconfigured set of wind turbines within the wind park, the **park model** simulates wind conditions on park and wind turbines scales in terms of turbulent flow fields (velocity vectors, pressure, power, and thrust). For this workflow step, the partner SINTEF provides solvers and models⁵ specialized on wind parks that can be executed by the Open-Source simulation system `OpenFoam`⁶.

Figure 1 shows the use of software containers to implement and to execute the workflow steps by means of Software Containers, as defined in D6.1 (Serial integration platform). We decided to use the implementation of Docker as basis for containerization, as it is the most popular container format, yet. It also provides capabilities for parallelized HPC, which is scope in work packages WP 6.3 and WP 6.4. As one contribution of Upwards is to provide the integration system with all components as

⁴ <https://www.mmm.ucar.edu/weather-research-and-forecasting-model>

⁵ Extensions of models provided by NREL/SOWFA <https://github.com/NREL/SOWFA>

⁶ <https://www.openfoam.com/>

Open Accessible Framework, we specified a concrete format that each container must follow to be used in Upwards, which means to be integrated within the workflow.

Figure 1: Upward's containerized wind park simulation workflow

Coupling procedure and data treatment of atmospheric outputs.

As stated above, WRF can resolve the motion of the atmospheric flows across many spatial and temporal scales. As a result, instantaneous 3D fields of wind speed components are obtained at a temporal frequency defined in “*wrf_output_frequency*” input entry.

However, as many CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) simulations in which the flow is driven by inflow conditions, the park simulation requires to impose fixed values of velocity at the inflow patch (i.e., cell's faces defining the inflow plane) at every given time. Therefore, in the following stages, we describe and illustrate the step-by-step procedure to transform WRF outputs to Park boundary conditions.

1. The WRF results (dependent on time, height, latitude, longitude) are extracted from the raw output files. For efficiency, only the values below $4 \cdot D$ (where D is the wind turbine diameter) above ground level are considered
2. As seen in Figure 2, latitude and longitude coordinates from the lambert conformal geographical projection are transform into a cartesian grid with UTM projection.

Figure 2: Illustration of WRF 3D domain at given time t

3. The time-dependent results are averaged into hourly values. The signal is smoothed further by doing a rolling average with a 2hr window.
4. As shown in Figure 3, wind direction is taken as the mean value of wind direction along a line of $4 \times D$ height from the ground for every time t .

Figure 3: Illustration of WRF surface representation of topography in a mountainous site together with vectors of the wind speed at a time t

5. Based on this value of wind direction, we create a plane, perpendicular to the wind direction vector, at a $10 \times D$ distance upstream from the domain's center (Figure 4 right).
6. The field of wind speed components (U, V, W) of the WRF solution are sampled onto that new plane, and then are averaged horizontally. Hence, a single wind profile is obtained (Figure 4 left).

Figure 4: Illustration of the mean vertical wind speed profile (left) obtained at the plane defined 10D upstream the domain’s centre at a given time t .

7. Finally, the vertical wind speed profile is replicated along the horizontal direction, to create a new plane which serve as inflow boundary condition to the Park simulation. An example of a plane of wind speed components is shown in Figure 5. These values are written in OpenFOAM plain text format.

Time after 2008-10-01: 0 (min)

Figure 5: Example of inflow conditions to the model Park created from the WRF-LES results.

2.1. Simulation models and systems

We manage WRF-LES and OpenFoam as software container images and respective build scripts (`Dockerfile`) in the collaboration platform Gitlab (see Data Management Plan in D.1.4 for more information). We provide each work package with an individual development branch. Figure 2 lists these development branches:

Workflow step	Encapsulated software	Repository location
atmospheric model (WP2)	WRF	https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/WP2/WP2%2Fwrf_docker
park model (WP2)	OPENFOAM	https://gitlab.itwm.fraunhofer.de/Adrian/upwards/-/tree/WP6/WP6%2Fcontainer%2Fdocker

Table 2: Overview of containers in Upwards

2.2. Data exchange interface

The data exchange interface defines the data format of initial conditions, model parameters, and simulation results. A convention in Upwards is that all input parameters are serialized in JSON notation in a file called `input_params.json`.

Atmospheric model

In this project, WRF is operated in *hindcast* mode, that is, it downscales past weather conditions from global reanalysis data, i.e., receives boundary and initial conditions, and by solving the thermodynamic governing equations of the atmosphere in very fine numerical grids, it can unveil the details of physical processes not seen by the global models occurring during those past weather events.

The current setup is based on the downscaling of the ERA5 reanalysis dataset, so it is possible to obtain the weather conditions of any period between 1979 until to-date (minus 1 month of ERA5 data availability), for any place in the world.

The system requires the following inputs in order to initialize and run WRF, as well as to serialize an inlet layer for the park model. As stated above, these inputs use the standardized JSON file format. Figure 6 shows an example content of the file `input_params.json`:

```
{
  "wind_farm_location":
  {
    "latitude"   : [57.049],
    "longitude"  : [8.886],
    "height"     : [263]
  },
  "rotor_diameter"      : 150,
  "dateLimits"          : ["2006-06-30 00:00", "2006-06-30 03:00"],
  "namelist_template_wps" : "namelist.wps.full_scale",
  "namelist_template_input" : "namelist.input.full_scale",
  "era5_data_frequency"   : 180,
  "wrf_output_frequency"  : 10,
  "what_to_do" :
  {
    "do_era5_download" : true,
    "do_vtk_output"    : true,
    "do_noise_output"  : true
  }
}
```

Figure 6: Input parameter of atmospheric model in JSON notation

The description of each entry can be found in the table below. The first three entries are case-dependent and site-specific, so they must be specified for every simulation. However, the next four entries can be fixed for all simulations. They are included to provide flexibility for testing the model as they give an easy access to different model's configuration parameters without the need of hardcoding it in the post-processing system.

Entry	Description
wind_farm_location	Values of the WGS84 coordinates (latitude °, longitude °) of the central location of the wind farm as well as the turbine height in meters.
rotor_diameter	Diameter of the turbine rotors of the farm (meters). So far, the same height is used for all turbines in the wind farm.
dateLimits	Simulation period (date from, date to) in the format: "yyyy-mm-dd HH:SS". See some notes about it below.
namelist_template*	Name of the namelists used for configuring the model. We have made two options available so far: full_scale dummy_for_testing, which are added to the name of the corresponding namelist. i.e. namelist.wps.xx and namelist.input.xx
era5_data_frequency	How often (in minutes) the ERA5 reanalysis data are to be ingested as driving conditions to WRF. The only values available are either 60, 180 or 360 min; (i.e 1, 3 or 6 hrs). In principle, the more often the better, as the reanalysis data is the closest depiction of reality we can get from the large-scale circulation at any given dates in the past. However, this choice increases the elapsed time of both, downloading the dataset from the European provider Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) and the time for the model preprocessing, which is currently done in a single processor. So, 180min is suggested as a good cost-efficient value.
wrf_output_frequency	How often you want the instantaneous output full field data from the model to be saved (in minutes). 10Min is a good choice. Bear in mind that in the full-scale case configuration, around 20GB of output data will be generated for a 3hr simulation period if 10min is selected. This size is increased or decreased linearly with the output frequency choice.
what_to_do	In order to provide some flexibility for the manual execution of the model, for either testing or for operational runs, it is possible to select whether you only want to download era5 files, whether you want to produce the bulky Vtk outputs (useful for visualization), or if you want or not to do the postprocessing for the inputs for the far-field acoustic model.

Care should be taken with the selection of the simulation period, which is set by the **dateLimits** entry. The simulation period should be less or equal to the **era5_data_frequency** value. On the other hand, it exists a problem in Numerical Weather Prediction simulations known as the *spinup* time. That is, the time that the components of a model require to reach an equilibrium with their own dynamics. While this time can be site and case-dependent, a range of 6 to 2 hrs prior to the period of interest is typically a safe choice.

Similar to the selection of maximum time length, the model can in principle be continuously run for any given period, however it is recommended to set maximum 1 week of integration for a single simulation. If longer periods are required, several weekly runs can be set and run individually, merging their outputs afterwards. In that case, just be careful to consider the additional spinup period.

Park model

The park model calculates the wind conditions in park and wind turbine scale within the area of the wind park. It requires initial conditions about:

- park dimensions (Computational domain size)
- initial distribution of wind velocity and pressure, settings of turbulence parameters such as turbulence intensity
- turbine types (e.g., NREL 5 MW, Siemens SWT 2.3, Upwards 15 MW)
- turbine positions and geometries (e.g., tower height, hub radius, tip radius, yaw angle, tilt angle)
- rotor states (e.g., rotation speed, pitch angle)
- Mesh configuration Simulation times (start, end, time step, write interval)

Figure 7 shows an example content of the file `input_params.json` in JSON notation. The framework of OPENFOAM allows plenty of more parameters to configure. We used the Python library PyFoam (<https://pypi.org/project/PyFoam/>) in our integration framework `py_upwards` to parse the complete configuration of OPENFOAM projects. This enabled us to list only those parameters that differ from default values into the `input_params.json`.

```
{
  'block_mesh_dimension': [ [-200, 126.2, 0],
                             [-200, 126.2, 400.0],
                             [-200, -126.2, 400.0],
                             [-200, -126.2, 0],
                             [757.2, 126.2, 0],
                             [757.2, 126.2, 400.0],
                             [757.2, -126.2, 400.0],
                             [757.2, -126.2, 0]],
  'delta_t': 0.02,
  'endTime': 100,
  'hex_mesh_dimensions': { 'turbine1': { 'point1': [-5, 0, 200.0],
                                         'point2': [5, 0, 200.0],
                                         'radius': 100,
                                         'type': 'searchableCylinder'}},
  'startTime': 0,
  'turbineArray': { 'globalProperties': { 'outputControl': "timeStep",
                                         'outputInterval': 1},
                   'turbine1': { 'Azimuth': 280.3935,
                                 'NacYaw': 270,
                                 'Pitch': 0,
                                 'RotSpeed': 10.9874,
                                 'baseLocation': [0, 0, 0],
                                 'bladeUpdateType': "oldPosition",
                                 'epsilon': 3.5,
                                 'fluidDensity': 1.25,
                                 'numBladePoints': 40,
                                 'pointDistType': "uniform",
                                 'pointInterpType': "linear",
                                 'rotationDir': "cw",
                                 'tipRootLossCorrType': "none",
                                 'turbineType': "NREL5MWRef"}},
  'turbine_locations': [(0, 0, 0)],
  'turbulentEpsilon': 0.55296,
  'turbulentKE': 0.96,
  'write_interval': 1000
}
```

Figure 7: Input parameter of park model in JSON notation

2.3. Flow field simulations in wind park scale

Based on the inflow conditions from WRF-LES, it is now possible to perform the wind park simulation. Figure 8 shows an example of a resulting flow conditions within the park.

Figure 8 Surface presenting the wind velocity on park level in x direction, shortly in front of a wind turbine rotor.

3. Conclusions

The explicit coupling between WRF-LES and Park model is a two-step workflow process:

1. Starting from the geo location of a planned wind park, the **atmospheric model** simulates spatial and temporal wind conditions (velocity, direction, pressure) on atmospheric scale. The partner AWST provides a tailored version of the Open Source LES-simulation system WRF (Weather Research and Forecast Model - WRF-LES).

2. Based on these wind conditions, and based on a preconfigured set of wind turbines within the wind park, the **park model** simulates wind conditions on park and wind turbine scales in terms of turbulent flow fields (velocity vectors, pressure). For this workflow step, the partner SINTEF provides solvers and models specialized on wind parks that can be executed by the Open Source simulation system OpenFoam.

Finally, the packaging and delivery of the **atmospheric model** as software container has been done according to the interface specification of D6.1 and D2.4. The runtime was extended with respect to enabling the HPC aspects of Task 6.3.